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Up-regulation of a mitochondrial pyruvate carrier (*MPC2*) in response to ERBB2 growth factor inhibition.

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Growth factor signaling pathways are prototypical signaling pathways whose basic characteristics in a cancer cell include a stereotyped feedback response behavior. EGFR family signaling pathways include ERBB1-4, like ERBB2 (HER2). Here we describe the mitochondrial pyruvate carrier *MPC2* as a gene product induced following growth factor inhibition in human cells.